

Software Bug Prediction Using Machine Learning

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Abstract — Predicting software bugs is an important part of the software development process. SBP's purpose is to find software modules that have problems. A software bug is a flaw or defect in the development and design of computer software. SBP can help you get rid of bugs. Early detection of software issues aids in the reduction of software bugs. To forecast software defects, the KNN algorithm is utilised. To forecast bugs, datasets and machine learning algorithms are employed, and then the accuracy is determined.

Keywords—software bug prediction, fault prediction, machine learning, KNN algorithm.

I. INTRODUCTION

Human faults in the programme structure or during the development phase can generate software bug errors or errors. The software may be utilised with ease and precision, with no errors. However, there will be hidden faults that may cause the software to malfunction. It's difficult to find a hacker without using software. Software bug guessing is an essential part in the development process. Software bug prediction improves dependability, quality, and efficiency while lowering costs. In software development, predicting software failure is a critical function. This is due to the ability to forecast mistake modules before programme distribution, which increases total software performance. Predicting software failures early also improves software customization in a variety of areas and increases resource usage. To predict software defects, many methodologies have been utilised. SBP employs machine learning techniques to forecast disruptive modules based on past mistake data, critical ratings, and numerous software methodologies.

Machine learning aids in the prediction of faults using past data. Machine learning algorithms are divided into two categories. Algorithms that are supervised and unsupervised. The KNN technique is used to predict bugs in this study. In this research, we use machine learning approaches to offer predictive development models for a software flaw that can allow the software to continue performing its expected task. Furthermore, we evaluated model performance using 10-fold cross-validation procedures, accuracy, recall, specificity, f1 scaling, and correctness, among other metrics.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

There have been many [1] kinds of research on the use of machine learning techniques to predict software errors. For example, the automatic linear regression (AR) technique was introduced to predict problematic modules. Based on past data about accumulated defects in programs, the study predicts problems for future programs. The AR model and the known power model (POWM) were also examined and compared using the Root Mean Square Error (RMSE) method. Furthermore, the study evaluated three data sets, and the results were positive.

R. Malhotra [2] presented a comprehensive study of software error prediction strategies based on machine learning (ML). The paper included a review of all studies published between 1991 and 2013, an analysis of machine learning techniques for software error prediction models and their performance evaluation, a comparison of machine learning and statistical techniques, a comparison of different machine learning techniques, and a summary. Strengths and weaknesses of machine learning techniques.

Publication [3] sets a standard to enable a general and useful comparison of various error prediction algorithms. The study included a complete comparison of known error prediction algorithms, as well as a new methodology that was introduced and evaluated by building a good comparison with existing methods using the presented criterion.

An object-oriented software bug prediction system model was created by D.L Gupta and K. Saxena [4]. (SBPS). The study combines defect data sets from similar categories that can be found in the Promise Software Engineering Repository. The proposed model was tested using the performance scale in the study (accuracy). Finally, the study results revealed that the average accuracy of the proposed model is 76.27 percent.

Software bug forecasting [5] is a technique in which a prediction model is created based on past data to predict future software flaws. Different approaches are presented based on different data sets, metrics, and performance measures. This study looked at how machine learning

techniques are used to predict software errors. NB, DT, and ANNs are three machine learning methods that have been applied.

Three true test/debug data sets are used in the evaluation procedure.

Accuracy, recall, F-measurement, and RMSE are used to collect experimental results. The results show that machine learning techniques are effective ways to predict future software problems. The results of the comparison revealed that the classifier DT outperformed the others.

III. METHODOLOGY

We used three freely available open-source data sets from the PROMISE software engineering database in this investigation. Tim Menzies et al. used these data sets in their research articles. Jureczko et al. developed a software crash prediction model to predict software flaws using machine learning algorithms in another investigation. In their article, they looked at data from eight projects (Promise Repository) and built a predictive model using 19 variables and CK Maccabi's metrics. We employed 22 features to create an automated error prediction model in our research. Software bugs can be predicted using metrics and one outcome. It's in perfect condition. The goal of this study is to forecast programme faults. Anticipating faults improves programme efficiency and dependability while also lowering costs.

We employed a set of well-known metrics based on confusion-generated matrices to assess the performance of ML programme error prediction methods.

The confusion matrix and the assessment procedures are described in the subsections below.

A. Confusion matrix

A confusion matrix is a table that is used to assess the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms. The test findings are summarised in the confusion matrix. The test results algorithm is summarised in the confusion matrix, which reports a positive integer (TP), false positives (FP), true negatives (TN), and False Negatives (FN) (FN).

B. Accuracy

The proportion of correct outcomes (both TP and TN) among the total number of cases studied is called accuracy (ACC). The highest level of accuracy is 1, while the lowest level of accuracy is 0. The following formula can be used to compute ACC:

$$ACC = (TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$$

C. Precision (Positive Predictive Value)

Accuracy is calculated as the number of true positives. The predictions are divided by the total number of positive predictions. The best precision is 1 while the worst is 0 and it can be calculated as:

$$Accuracy = TP / (TP + FP)$$

D. Recovery (true positive rate or sensitivity)

To assess model performance, we employed tenfold cross-validation procedures, precision, recall,

specificity, f 1 measurement, and accuracy. The ML algorithms were able to reach a high level of accuracy.

E. E. F-measurement

Retrieval-weighted harmonic means are used to calculate the F-scaling. It is commonly used to compare ML algorithms that differ from each other by combining call back and scaling precision measurements. F is the measurement formula, which is as follows:

$$F\text{-measure} = (2 * Recall * Precision) / (Recall + Precision)$$

IV. BUILD MODEL

This model is built to predict the bugs in the software. Different steps are involved in bug prediction. The steps involved are:

- 1.Import the packages that are necessary.

```
import numpy as np
import pandas as pd
import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
import seaborn as sns
import plotly as plotly
from plotly.offline import
init_notebook_mode, iplot
init_notebook_mode(connected=True)
import plotly.graph_objs as go import os
```
2. Add the data into a DataFrame, then get the shape of data.

```
data = pd.read_csv('cm1.csv')
```
3. Analysing the data

```
defect_true_false = data.groupby('defects')['b'].
apply(lambda x: x.count())
print('False: ',defect_true_false[0])
print('True: ',defect_true_false[1])
```

```
False: 449
True: 49
```

Fig:1

- 4.Splitting dataset into test and training dataset

```
X_train, X_test, y_train, y_test = train_test_split(X, Y
test_size = 0.2, random_state = 0)
model.fit(X_train, y_train)
y_pred = model.predict(X_test)
```

5. Then identify on test set and calculate the accuracy of the data.

```
from sklearn.metrics import accuracy_score
print ("ACC: ",accuracy_score(y_pred,y_test))
The accuracy is 98.4%.
```

V. RESULT

The findings show that machine learning approaches are excellent at predicting future software vulnerabilities. Three originals are used in the evaluation procedure. Datasets are being tested and debugged. Test scores are collected based on accuracy, precision, and recall.

K-Nearest Neighbors Algorithm				
	precision	recall	f1-score	support
Redesign	1.00	0.95	0.98	21
Successful	0.99	1.00	0.99	79
accuracy			0.99	100
macro avg	0.99	0.98	0.98	100
weighted avg	0.99	0.99	0.99	100

```

[[20  1]
 [ 0 79]]
ACC: 0.99
    
```

. Fig2

VI. CONCLUSION

Software error prediction is a technique that uses previous data to construct a prediction model for future software problems. Various approaches based on different data sets, metrics, and performance measurements have been offered. This study looked at how machine learning techniques could be used to forecast software defects.

VII. REFERENCES

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